

On becoming a spatial agent: A comparative analysis of transdisciplinary design and build studio pedagogy in Cyprus and Sweden

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Keywords: transdisciplinarity, design and build pedagogy, live studio, spatial agency, commons

1. Introduction

As the traditional design studio becomes increasingly obsolete in the face of complex and multi-faceted realities, architectural education is in urgent need of profound restructuring (Awan et al., 2011; Doucet, 2017; Salazar Ferro et al., 2020). For several decades, the live studio framework, *i.e.* a framework that exposes students to the contingencies of a “real-world” experience, intertwined with a web of spatial, social, environmental and political aspects, has been challenging the archetype of the architect, allowing for a proliferation of the ways of being-in-context for students, educators, institutions and communities alike (Abrahams et al., 2021). There is, however, room for further exploration in the ways in which the live studio is interpreted and implemented, within a rising post-capitalist wave of thought, both in the different geographical and cultural contexts, but also in its ideological standpoint and underpinnings.

The aim of this paper is to contribute to the ongoing discussion on reshaping live studio architectural education as a transformative and transdisciplinary pedagogy geared towards design activism, direct action and reclaiming learning as a commons that transcends the boundaries of academia (Bollier, 2021). More specifically, this paper will reflect on the opportunities, implications, as well as the limitations of a situated, transdisciplinary, design & build studio as a hub for training future architects in becoming socially conscious spatial agents, able to assess and respond effectively to complex challenges and work collectively towards a common future.

2. From architecture to spatial agency

Spatial agency is a term that illustrates the gradual moving away from architecture and the way it has been established as a practice through the modern era. It seeks to highlight a transdisciplinary practice of synergy-forming that puts “spatial judgement, mutual knowledge and critical awareness” at the forefront (Lorne, 2017). The value of synergies has been illustrated by the steadily rising adoption of co-creation methods over the past decades, both in practice, and education.

Through co-creation processes in architecture pedagogy, *i.e.* the live studio, students are exposed to unique contributions where everyone’s competences, knowledge and lived experiences can be recognised, highlighted and utilised. The entanglement of all the different knowledge and meanings can create connections and reconfigurations can challenge the primacy of established pre-conceptions of what is each participant’s role, be it student,

educator, or stakeholder and allows for multiple ways of an individual's situatedness (Abrahams et al., 2021). Therefore knowledge & knowledge production become a “commons” that can be co-produced in a reflexive and exploratory way, which allows for fresh ideas to emerge. Design & build as a method of learning can add the element of praxis in the form of a tangible and immediate impact in space. Knowledge co-production, in this sense, moves away from theorisation and exercise-on-paper to the neighbourhood and the city, thus breaking the barrier between academia and society in a most direct way.

2.1 Case studies

In exploring how can a transdisciplinary design & build studio impact student perception, two case studies are selected: The first one is a design & build workshop in the University of Cyprus (department of Architecture), which is directly linked to the 2nd year “co-creating urban commons” studio. The second is the summer design & build course called “DARE to Build” offered by Chalmers University of Technology to master students of the Department of Architecture and Civil Engineering. In Table 1, the two courses are presented through relevant basic descriptors.

Table 1. The two courses illustrated through basic descriptors

	Co-creating Urban Commons (CY)	DARE to Build (SE)
Initiating Entity	University of Cyprus	Chalmers University of Technology
Objective/Vision/Agenda	Expose future graduates to real-world contingencies through a collaborative, co-creation framework illustrated through the interaction with different agents and disciplines as well as with practice while at the same time promoting engagement and a sense of responsibility towards the commons.	Reconcile the disparity between monodisciplinary education and multi-disciplinary practice, while at the same time creating impact and outreach in local communities.
Students	2nd, 3rd and 4th year architecture students	Master students, engineers and architects
Educational methods	Urban Living Lab, design & build	Problem-and-project-based learning (PPBL), design & build, CDIO (conceive, design, implement, operate)
Urban Context	Latsia Municipality (suburban Nicosia)	Million home programme (Miljonprogrammet) suburban areas in Gothenburg
Scale/Location	Neighbourhood-level interventions, Nicosia, Cyprus	Neighbourhood-level interventions, Gothenburg, Sweden
Status/Runtime	2022-	2018-
Duration & Pace	3 weeks, full time (5 ECTS)	5 weeks, fulltime (7,5 ECTS)
Stakeholders & Partnerships	Latsia Municipality, Nicosia Development Agency, local community	Municipality of Gothenburg, local housing companies, local community

By perceiving live projects as case studies that fall under the broader scope of urban studies, this comparative analysis adopts the viewpoint of scholars within the field, such as Jennifer Robinson and Manuel Aalbers; they argue for a proliferation of comparative analyses that move beyond clusters of similarity and pre-established theorisations of places (e.g. comparing housing policies of northern European countries between themselves because the “global south” is just too different) towards a more relational approach, fortified by a reflexive process, and a postcolonial lens (Aalbers, 2022; Robinson, 2016). Sweden and Cyprus, two national contexts with diverse cultural, socio-political environmental and economic characteristics provide an interesting testbed for a comparative analysis that aims to move away from contrasting through either a western superiority perspective or a romanticised reading of local practices, to a search for common trajectories. Furthermore, prior familiarity with both contexts presents an opportunity of ethnographic strategies and elements that can be incorporated and enhance the analysis (Ronald, 2011).

2.2 Methods

This comparative analysis aims to provide insight on the impact of a transdisciplinary design & build pedagogical model on student perceptions regarding their positioning as future professionals, their attitude towards processes of cooperation and co-creation with various stakeholders, as well as their confidence levels regarding transdisciplinary, hands-on teamwork. To achieve this, the study draws on social sciences methodologies within a participatory action research (PAR) framework; a set of two questionnaires was handed out to the participating students of both courses (Figures 1 and 2), one in the beginning of each course and one at their completion, in order to trace and document both the collective and the individual shifts in mindsets and perceptions. Within the PAR framework, a reflexive insider researcher perspective methodology is used, solidified both by the aforementioned prior familiarity with these contexts in both a macro (cultural, historical) and a micro (educational, interpersonal) level, and by an active and immersed role as a teacher throughout the process. This position enabled the enrichment of the research process by building bonds of trust between those involved, through which observation and in-depth analysis of formal (focus group session) and informal, everyday interactions was facilitated, while working collaboratively towards a common goal.

Figure 1. UCY students posing while sitting on a cement block bench that they designed & built. Source: Effrosyni Roussou

Figure 2. Chalmers students enjoying celebratory cake after the completion of the outdoor classroom. Source: Effrosyni Roussou

3. Conclusion

To sum up, the expected outcome of this exploration is a set of observations on the limitations and opportunities of a transformative design & build pedagogy as well as the ways in which it impacts the (self) perception of future architects. By tracing the common trajectories of the two study cases, embedded in their own cultural, economic, environmental and socio-political contexts, the scope of impact identification is broadened to shed light on aspects of this matter that may exist beyond educational methods and curriculum structure. Preliminary analysis reveals interesting questions regarding the correlation of long-term sustaining co-creation processes and shifts in students' perception. Overall, steps in this direction of education can directly contribute to a better-informed architectural education, able to guide students through the necessary shift in perception in the present that may secure better practitioners in the future.

Acknowledgment

This paper is an output of E. Roussou's doctoral research, conducted under the auspices of RE-DWELL, an Innovative Training Network (ITN) funded by the H2020 Marie Skłodowska-Curie programme of the European Union (2020-24), with project number 956082.

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